

INTERFACIAL SHEAR STRENGTH (IFSS) OF DUAL BASALT FIBERS REINFORCED POLYCARBONATE COMPOSITES (DFC) SPECIMENS AND THEIR MICRO-FAILURE MECHANISMS USING ACOUSTIC EMISSION (AE)

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ABSTRACT

Interfacial shear strength (IFSS) between fiber and matrix in dual basalt fibers (98 μm and 15 μm) reinforced polycarbonate (PC) composites (DFC) were investigated through fragmentation method and acoustic emission (AE) technique. Using amino-silane coupling agent, the IFSS under wet condition showed much higher improvement compared to that in the IFSS under dry condition due to chemical and hydrogen bondings in two interphases among basalt fiber/silane coupling agent/PC matrix. Monitoring of AE during straining DFC specimens showed the sequential occurrence of three distinct groups of AE data. First two groups may come from fiber breakages of two different diameters, and the third comes from mainly matrix cracking. By setting the appropriate threshold level, one-to-one correspondence between the number of AE events and fiber breakages was established. This AE method can be correlated successfully to the IFSS via the fragmentation technique.

INTRODUCTION

Interfacial shear strength (IFSS) between fiber and matrix is one of the most important factors in characterizing the mechanical properties of fiber reinforced composites. If the IFSS is too low, it is hard to expect the performance of reinforcing fibers in composites, whereas if the IFSS is too high, there is a decrease in fracture

toughness of composites because of the poor resistance to the stress crack propagation. Hence, it is necessary that the IFSS should be determined via the optimization rather than maximization for the purpose.

Several micro-mechanical techniques were proposed for measuring the IFSS in fiber reinforced composites. Some of the most frequently used techniques include the single fiber pull-out test [1], the single fiber composites (SFC) test [2], and the microindentation method [3]. Among them, the SFC test method, originally proposed by Kelly and Tyson [4] for the application to the fiber/metal composite system, is to give comparatively abundant informations (e.g., the interfacial failure mode as well as the IFSS) using only several specimens. Based on the forced balance in a micromechanical model, Kelly and Tyson showed that the critical fragment length ℓ_c is given by

$$\ell_c = d \sigma_f / 2\tau \quad (1)$$

where d is the fiber diameter, σ_f is the fiber fracture stress, and τ is the IFSS.

The data for both fragment length and fiber strength can be approximated by lognormal distributions, and these have been combined by a theory developed to yield a lognormal distribution for IFSS by Own et. al. [5]. Some authors [6] have assumed a uniform fragment length distribution with a mean ℓ_c , of $0.75\ell_c$. Henstenburg and Phoenix [7] have developed a refined model of the fragmentation process based on the Poisson/Weibull flaws along the fiber length and a linear buildup of the fiber tensile strength away from the fiber fracture locations. They developed a relationship which facilitated the formulation of the model as a Monte Carlo simulation in terms of a single factor, the Weibull shape parameter, ρ , for fiber strength. Along with simulating the non-dimensional fiber fragment length distribution, they showed that

$$\tau = (d \sigma_f / 2 \ell_c) (\Lambda_p / 2)^{(P + 1)/P} \quad (2)$$

where σ_f is the Weibull scale parameter for the fiber strength at a gauge length equal to the mean fragment length, ℓ . The quantity Λ_p is the non-dimensional mean aspect ratio (ℓ/h), where h is a certain characteristic length which is also derived from their model. However, it is known that neither the Weibull distribution nor the lognormal distribution provides a superior fit for the most of cases.

The most works of the SFC method has been applied to the thermosetting resin-based composite systems so far. Here, modified DFC specimens can provide direct comparison between the untreated and the treated cases, which can save time and give exact same conditions.

In the present study, the effects of surface treatment using amino-silane coupling agent on the IFSS and micro-failure mechanism for the basalt fiber/PC composite have been evaluated with the aids of fragmentation method and acoustic emission (AE). In addition, the effect of amino-silane coupling agent on the durability under wet conditions was also investigated compared to the case under dry conditions. Using same DFC specimens, nondestructive AE method was applied to characterize the failure of fiber and PC cracking while straining. Those results were correlated with each other.

EXPERIMENTALS

Materials

Basalt fiber: Basalt fiber was made from naturally occurring basalt rock in the Pullman, WA area (U.S.A.), which has the main composition SiO_2 , 48%, Al_2O_3 , 14%; FeO , 12%, CaO , 9.5%; and MgO , 5%. The fiber was produced in a prototype device. The diameters of the fibers used were mostly 15 μm . Also, by controlling winding speed slowly, 98 μm diameter was prepared specially. There was no special fiber treatment procedure. The virgin fiber strength, varying in the range 2-4 GPa depending on the drawing conditions, is comparable to that of E-glass fibers; the modulus is 85 GPa.

Silane coupling agents: Silane coupling agents were purchased from Petrarch Systems Co. (Bristol, PA) and used without further purification. 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (A0750) was obtained as the neat compound. The silane were diluted to the required concentration in aqueous solvents for application on basalt fiber.

Polycarbonate (PC) matrix: The matrix resin chosen for this study was polycarbonate (PC), supplied by Samyang Hwasung Co. (Korea) in a form of granulate. As a mold releasing material, the commercially available polyimide film sheet (Air-Tech. International Co., U.S.A.) was used.

Methods

Measurement of Single Fiber Strength: The each diameter of about fifty carbon fibers used was determined using the optical microscope attached with calibrated eye piece lense. Test specimens for measuring the tensile strength of basalt fibers with gauge length, 2, 5, 10, 20, and 100 mm. Test specimens were made by placing the single basalt fiber on the straw-board frame with each gauge length, fixing by Scotch tapes in the center line on both ends, and hardening using epoxy adhesives (Fig. 1). The tensile strengths were measured using the small sized Instron at a cross-head speed of 1mm/min, and with 1Kg load cell. About fifty samples were tested for above each gauge lengths for adequate statistical analysis.

Preparation of DFC specimen: Two basalt fibers were laid down unidirectionally in the center place of two PC sheets parallel to them, then fixed with Scotch tapes. They were covered with two pieces of polyimide sheets on both sides, and again covered with two steel plates on the top of the sheet to give a certain weight, then heated to 250 °C on the hot plate to be melted for certain periods. After being melted sufficiently, they were put into the cold water, then being cut to produce dogbone-shaped DFC specimens. Using Instron using 10Kg load cell, stress and strain curves of DFC specimen were obtained.

Interfacial Shear Strength (IFSS) Measurements: For the IFSS measurements, dual fiber cast in a polymer resin to produce a dog-bone shaped specimen as shown in Fig. 2(a), with two fibers aligned along the longitudinal axis. During testing, the specimen is incrementally stressed, and the fiber undergoes multiple fracture within the matrix are measured *in situ* using polarized-light microscopy. Single fiber fragmentation

procedure with increasing tensile load are shown in the Fig. 2(b).

The ultimate fragment lengths are approximated to equal the critical length for stress transfer, l_c , which is related to the fiber diameter, d , tensile strength, σ_f , and the IFSS, τ , through the expression, $l_c / d = \sigma_f / 2\tau$. The data for both fragment length and fiber strength may be approximated by lognormal distributions, and these have been combined by lognormal distribution for the IFSS [6].

If the fiber strength and critical aspect ratio (CAR) are distributed with lognormal means μ_1 , μ_2 and lognormal deviation σ_1 , σ_2 , respectively, the IFSS can also be distributed with a lognormal mean μ_3 and lognormal deviation σ_3 , defined as

$$\mu_3 = \mu_1 - \mu_2 - \ln(2) \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_3^2 = \sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2 \quad (4)$$

and the actual IFSS distribution is thus obtained in closed form. If the fiber strength and/or CAR follow different distributions, a numerical solution is possible. If the IFSS follows a lognormal distribution with lognormal mean μ and lognormal deviation σ , the mean and variance values of the IFSS are given by

$$\text{Mean} = \exp(\mu + \sigma^2/2) \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Variance} = \{\exp(2\mu + \sigma^2)\} \{\exp(\sigma^2) - 1\} \quad (6)$$

In order to evaluate the effect of moisture exposure on the IFSS, the DFC specimens were immersed in boiling water, 100 °C for 1 hour. The IFSS was then measured after equilibration of the specimens for 1 hour at room temperature.

Acoustic emission (AE) Measurement: DFC specimen was placed on the specially designed tensile machine with increasing tensile. AE sensor was attached to the center of the DFC specimen. After AE test was ended, the number of fragmentation of fiber and the micro-failure in the DFC specimen were observed via polarized microscopy. AE signals were detected by a wideband type sensor (model WD by PAC) with maximum sensitivity of -60 dB (ref. 1V/ μ bar) at 550 kHz. The sensor output was only amplified by 60 dB at preamplifier then fed into an AE signal processing unit, AET5500 system, where AE parameters were extracted. The threshold level was set to 100 μ V at the sensor. Two AE parameters, peak amplitude and energy, were investigated for the time and the distribution analysis. In addition, frequency analysis of waveforms by the fast Fourier transform (FFT) was used to characterize the failure mode of each test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effects on Preparation Conditions of DFC Specimens and their IFSS under Dry and Wet Conditions

Table 1 showed the fiber shape and PC matrix condition for various typed-DFC specimens as a function of melting temperature and time. An optimum temperature for melting was in the range of 250 to 270 °C. Within 40 min. at 250 °C, resin did not

melt, whereas for longer melting time such as more than 100 min. at 270 °C, matrix was too melt to make fiber to be curve-shaped. And, after matrix being melted, specimen was quenched in cold water to give higher elongation. Table 2 showed untreated fiber tensile strength and elongation for 5 different gauge lengths. As gauge length increases, tensile strength and elongation decrease, due to randomly distributed defects on fiber surfaces and heterogeneity between different fibers.

Fig. 3 showed the stress-strain curves of two typed dogbone-shaped specimens for two different cooling conditions. In slow cooling case elongation value was to be relatively small, because relatively less ductile specimen was broken before necking to be continued. In contrast to this, quick cooling case showed much larger elongation compared to the slow cooling case, which is macro-mechanically due to the progressed necking phenomenon based on plastic deformation. Tensile modulus values from the curves were 1.32 GPa and 1.45 GPa for quick and slow cooling procedures, respectively.

Fig. 4 showed the IFSS of DFC specimen treated with 0.5 wt% amino-silane under dry and wet conditions. The IFSS under wet condition after 1 hour in boiling water showed much higher improvement % compared to that in the IFSS under dry condition. It may be because of chemical bonding in the interphase between functional group in basalt fiber surface and silane coupling agent, and because of hydrogen bonding in another interphase between silane coupling agent and PC matrix.

Acoustic Emission Analysis using DFC Specimens and Correlation with the IFSS

In addition to the direct observation of fiber fragmentation using polarizing microscope, AE accompanying the fiber fracture was also monitored by a piezoelectric transducer positioned at the center of the DFC specimen. It was of interest to follow the sequence of fiber fracture and microcracking of the PC resin on the fiber for correlation of the AE events with the different failure processes.

Fig. 5 showed one-to-one correspondence between fiber break and AE events, based on the well-separated AE events distribution for the fiber breakage and matrix cracking. By setting the appropriate threshold level during the measurement, low energy AE data associated with PC matrix cracking can be filtered off to obtain the AE data with high energy due to mainly fiber fracture. This AE method can be correlated successfully to the fragmentation technique to measure the IFSS by counting average number of fiber breakages. These can suggest that AE method can be another technique to measure the IFSS more easily than the fragmentation method. The method would be particularly useful in the case of opaque or dark-colored resin systems, where visual observation of fragment lengths is not possible.

Fig. 6 (a) showed the AE amplitude and AE energy for 98 and 15 μm basalt fibers embedded DFC specimen as a function of measuring time. Fig. 6 (b) showed three distinct groups in the distributions of AE amplitude and AE energy. Three main groups were well separated in terms of different ranges for both AE amplitude and AE energy. In Fig. (a), fiber fracture of large 98 μm diameter can cause big matrix crack to be shown lower range of AE output sources, whereas 15 μm fiber did not show any following matrix AE output due to low fracture energy source. In addition, due to rather brittle nature of large diameter fiber started to break in advance than 15 μm fiber case. Due to the effect of large burst energy matrix events were shown only in

the 98 μm fiber case, whereas in the 15 μm case there are little AE event from matrix cracks, probably due to small size fracture energy by matrix cracking to be detected hardly by the threshold level.

Fig. 7 showed typical AE waveforms generated during tensile test and their FFT results. The 98 μm fibers generated very large AE signals compared to the 15 μm fibers. The waveform in the 98 μm fiber case showed characteristic peak frequency at 280 KHz mainly due to fiber breakage, whereas in the 15 μm fiber case some high frequency components around 400–600 KHz as well as at 280 KHz appeared. This is probably because of complex failure mechanisms such as debonding, matrix cracking, or combined failure mechanism as well as fiber breaks frequency at 280 KHz.

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CONCLUSIONS

Effects on amino-silane coupling agent of interfacial shear strength (IFSS) for two different diameter-basalt fibers/polycarbonate composites (DFC) were investigated via fragmentation test and acoustic emission method. Obtained results are as follows:

- Tensile strength and elongation for basalt fibers decrease with increasing gauge lengths, due to heterogeneous distribution of flaws on the fiber surface. Improvement of the IFSS by amino-silane treatment was much higher under wet conditions compared to that under dry conditions, due to chemical bondings in the interphases.
- In the DFC specimens well distinct three distribution groups were exhibited from AE event. Also characteristic peak frequencies from fibers breakages of two different diameter were observed by FFT analysis. One-to-one correspondence between the AE events and fiber breakage was established, which can result in another method to calculate the IFSS more easily in especially opaque or dark-colored specimens.

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Fig. 1. Paper Frame and Attached Fiber to Measure a Single Fiber Tensile Strength.

Table 1. Optimized Conditions of DFC Specimens for Various Holding Time on the Hot Plate, and their IFSS.

Heating Temp. (°C)	Heating Time (min)	Fiber Shape in DFC	PC Matrix Condition
240	40	—	not melted
250	40	straight	melted
270	40	straight	melted
	60	straight	melted
	100	curve	too melted
300	40	curve	degradation

Table 2. Tensile Strength of Basalt Fiber Coated with Various Gauge Lengths.

Gauge Length (mm)	No. of Specimen	Diameter (μm)	Elongation (%)	Tensile Strength (MPa)
2	43	15.6	5.53 (1.46)	2018 (340) ¹⁾
5	44	15.3	3.88 (0.83)	1977 (247)
10	47	15.5	3.16 (0.53)	1922 (228)
20	48	15.4	2.57 (0.49)	1833 (316)
100	46	15.2	1.34 (0.44)	1179 (368)

¹⁾ Standard deviation.

Fig. 3. Stress-Strain Curve of PC Dogbone-Shaped DFC Specimens using Two Different Cooling Types.

Fig. 2. (a) Dogbone-Shaped Single Fiber Composite Specimens; (b) Graphic Representation of the Evolution of Failures and the Corresponding Stress Profiles in the Embedded Fiber During DFC Test.

Fig. 4. Improvement % of IFSS by using Amino-Silane Coupling Agent under Dry and Wet Conditions.

Fig. 5. One-to-One Correspondence between Fiber Breakage and the Number of AE Event for the DFC Specimens with two Different Diameter Fibers, 98 and 15 μm.

Fig. 6. (a). AE Amplitude and AE Energy for 98 and 15 μ m Basalt Fiber Embedded DFC Specimen as a Function of Measuring Time; (b) AE Amplitude and Energy Distribution in DFC Specimen.

Fig. 7. AE Waveforms from DFC Specimen while Straining and FFT Results.